

Eliminating the geometric error in tissue conductivity measurements by increasing the sample size

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In this study we simulated the tissue conductivity measurement with two-electrode probe in contact with the samples of different size. We found that after the sample reaches about twice the size of the probe, further increase in the size of the sample does not affect the resulting conductance. For smaller sizes of the sample we found that conductance decreases significantly. This decrease in conductance causes the underestimation of the conductivity of the sample. This error is caused by the limited geometry of the sample hence the geometric error. The geometric error can be avoided by ensuring the size of the sample is sufficiently larger than the probe, either by having large enough samples or by decreasing the size the probe.

Introduction

Knowledge of the electrical conductivity of biological tissues at low frequencies (i.e. below 100 kHz) is fundamental for medical electromagnetic applications, however it is still limited due to the measurement challenges, including electrode polarization (EP) [1].

One application of electrical conductivity measurements is in electroporation assessment. Since electroporation causes an immediate increase in cell membrane permeability that results in membrane conductivity increase, conductivity measurement offer the possibility to perform real-time assessment of the electroporation phenomenon in a minimally invasive fashion [2].

The factor which relates the measured conductance with the sample conductivity is known as the cell constant k and it characterises the measurement cell. The value of k depends only on the cell geometry [3] and it can be determined by calculation (when the geometry of the cell is simple) [4] or it can be determined experimentally by measuring the conductance of standard liquids with known conductivity [5].

When two-electrode probe is used for measurement of the conductivity of biological tissues, the measurement cell is comprised of both the probe and the sample. Therefore the geometry of the standard used to determine the cell constant must match the geometry of the sample, unless both can be considered infinite [3]. Any mismatch in the geometry of the two will result in a geometric error – the cell constant determined for the geometry of the standard is not adequate to represent the geometry of the measurement cell when measuring the conductivity of the sample.

Since it is not possible to match the geometry for every case, in this study we examine the minimum size of the sample required to eliminate the geometric error. In the case when further increase in the size of the sample does not change the conductance, the assumption can be made that the current flows mostly unimpeded by the limited extents of the geometry of the sample. From the perspective of the probe the sample would appear as infinite. For smaller size of the sample the decrease in conductance would cause the underestimation of the conductivity of the sample due to the geometric error.

Methods

In this study we simulated two circular electrodes in contact with the samples of different size. The radius of the electrodes was $r_e = 3$ mm and the distance between the electrodes was $d_e = 16$ mm. The material of the electrodes was copper ($\sigma = 5.998e7$ S/m). The base model of the sample was a cylinder with radius $r_s = 25$ mm, and depth $d_s = 30$ mm. In the first part the dimensions of the samples were scaled up by the factor ranging from 1-10. In the second part only the depth of the sample was scaled down by the factor ranging from 0.1-1. The radius of the sample was not decreased in the second part as the sample has to be wide enough to fit the electrodes. The conductivity of the sample was set to be in the range of conductivity of biological tissues ($\sigma = 0.703$ S/m).

We used COMSOL AC/DC Module to run the total of 20 simulations. The voltage between the electrodes was set to $U = 100 \text{ V}$ and the results of the simulations included the electric field distribution within the sample, conductance and total current.

Results

We found that further increase in size of the sample from factor 2 (resulting radius $r_s = 50 \text{ mm}$ and depth $d_s = 60 \text{ mm}$) did not change the conductance and therefore would not change the calculated conductivity. For smaller sizes of the sample we found that the conductance decreases significantly (Figure 1).

Conclusion

This decrease in simulated conductance causes the underestimation of the conductivity of the sample due to the geometric error. In the case when the sample is twice the size of the probe (and larger) we can make the assumption that the current flows unimpeded by the limited extents of the sample. In the case when the sample is smaller, the current flowing through the sample is impeded by the limited extent of the sample. The geometric error can be avoided by ensuring the size of the sample is large enough compared to the size of the probe. If the size of the sample is small, the geometric error can be avoided by decreasing the size the probe.

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Figures

Figure 1. Conductance and the corresponding geometric error for different sizes of the sample. The size of the sample is represented by the scale factor. For the scale factors of 1 and larger both the radius and the depth of the sample are scaled. For the scale factors smaller than 1 only the depth is scaled. The base sample size before scaling is $r = 25$ mm and $d = 30$ mm. For all sizes with the scale factor larger than 2 the geometric error is eliminated.